

PARTNERS

GET IN TOUCH!

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No [875187]

WHAT IS USER-CHI?

LOOKING FOR A EUROPE WHERE ELECTRIC VEHICLE CHARGING IS WIDESPREAD, EFFICIENT AND WORKS FOR USERS?

Look no further than **USER-CHI**. Industry powered, city driven and user-centric, USER-CHI will co-create and demonstrate smart solutions around 7 connecting nodes of the Mediterranean and Scandinavian-Mediterranean Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) corridors between February 2020 – January 2024 to boost a massive e-mobility market take-up in Europe.

OBJECTIVES

USER-CHI WILL UNLOCK THE MASSIVE POTENTIAL OF ELECTROMOBILITY IN EUROPE BY:

Designing electric charging networks around **user needs**

Deploying an **interoperability** framework and platform

Enhancing scalable infrastructure roll-out by means of **smart grid integration**

Developing **marketable, innovative** and highly **convenient** charging systems

Co-designing and demonstrating novel and **sustainable business and market models**

Making legal and regulatory **recommendations** for a massive **deployment** of electric vehicles

USER-CHI PRODUCTS

To deliver its strategic objectives, USER-CHI will design and develop a set of solutions covering all aspects of a massive deployment of electric vehicles:

CLICK – CHARGING LOCATION AND HOLISTIC PLANNING KIT:

An online tool for the location planning of new charging infrastructure in cities and TEN-T corridors.

STATIONS OF THE FUTURE HANDBOOK:

Guidelines and recommendations to design the perfect user-centric charging station of the future.

eMoBEST – e-MOBILITY REPLICATION AND BEST PRACTICE CLUSTER:

A collaboration platform to facilitate the transfer of best practices among the demonstration and replication cities.

INFRA – INTEROPERABILITY FRAMEWORK:

A package of rules, guidelines and recommendations that will support highly interoperable processes among the electromobility stakeholders.

INCAR – INTEROPERABILITY, CHARGING AND PARKING PLATFORM:

A platform providing roaming and barrier-free access to EV charging points and offering related innovative integrated services for the EV drivers.

SMAC – SMART CHARGING TOOL:

A tool providing smart grid integration and demand management services for slow, medium, fast and ultrafast charging.

INSOC – INTEGRATED SOLAR DC CHARGING FOR LIGHT ELECTRIC VEHICLES (LEVs):

A solution combining charging, onsite production of renewable energy and theft-proof parking for Light Electric Vehicles.

INDUCAR – INDUCTIVE CHARGING FOR E-CARS:

A wireless and highly automated charging solution for e-cars.

USER-CHI CITIES

THE USER-CHI SOLUTIONS WILL BE DEMONSTRATED IN 5 URBAN AREAS ALL ALONG THE EUROPEAN TERRITORY:

Barcelona metropolitan area (Spain), Berlin (Germany), Budapest (Hungary), Rome (Italy), and Turku (Finland).

Since large scale replication and transferability of USER-CHI results is one of the cornerstones of the project, two replication cities - Murcia and Florence - will replicate select solutions.

TEN-T Corridors

Scandinavian-Mediterranean

Mediterranean

